

ISic1369

I.Sicily inscription 1369

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Catina

Place of origin (modern)

Catania

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Catania, Museo Civico di

Catania, inventory 718

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Ἐνθάδε κίτε
2. Σωτηρίς τελευ
3. τᾷ τῆι πρὸς καλ(αν)
4. δῶν Δεκενβρί
5. ω[ν] ζήσασα ἔτη
6. ν Χρησιανή
- 7.

Apparatus

Korhonen 2004. While Korhonen reads on l.3 πρὸς, Amico reads ΠΡΟϜ,
Torremuzza reads ΠΡΟς, Kaibel emends πρὸς γ'

Translation (en)

Here lies Soteris, met her end 6(?) days before the Kalends of December, having lived for 50 years, [chresiane?]

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492982

EDCS 39101749

PHI 140874

PHI 316277

Bibliography

Kaibel, G. 1890. Inscriptiones Graecae Siciliae et Italiae, additis graecis Galliae Hispaniae, Britanniae, Germaniae inscriptionibus. *Inscriptiones Graecae consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae Editae. Volumen XIV.* Berlin. At 14.0550 (<https://clio.columbia.edu/catalog/6873760>)

Korhonen, K. 2004. Le iscrizioni del Museo civico di Catania : storia delle collezioni, cultura epigrafica, edizione. Helsinki. At 197

Boeckh, A., Franz, J., Curtius, E., Kirchhoff, A., Roehl, H. 1828-1887. Corpus Inscriptionum Graecarum. Berlin. At 4.9481

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